

Mineral Characteristics of Tinpahari Bentonite Clay

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Several complementary analytical techniques, such as infrared spectroscopy, X ray diffraction and Mössbauer spectroscopy have been used to find the complete mineralogical characterisation of a bentonite clay, from the Tinpahari region of Sahibganj district (Bihar State). It has been concluded that the Tinpahari bentonite clay is a 'mixed-layer minerals' clay comprising dioctahedral illite chlorite and vermiculite silicate minerals. The gradation of Tinpahari clay has been suggested as between illite and montmorillonite clay.

THE Tinpahari region of Sahibganj District in Bihar State is endowed with rich clay belonging to montmorillonite or more commonly known as bentonite clays. This type of clay because of its unique physicochemical properties, is finding increasingly large usage as a material of great industrial importance. Many of the important physicochemical properties of such clays are closely related to their structure. As such detailed systematic studies on their crystal structure and of the mineralogical characterisation of these clays are rather imperative.

The present paper concerns itself with the characterisation of the minerals present in the Tinpahari bentonite clay, for which several complementary analytical techniques such as infrared spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, and Mössbauer spectroscopy have been made use of.

Experimental

The procedure for the preparation of clay samples, their separation into different particle size fraction following the sedimentation method and other details of the experiment are reported in our other communications¹⁻³. The chemical analysis of the clay as also its surface area and cation-exchange capacity are given in Table 1.

For X-ray diffractometry, a Philips PW-1011 X-ray diffractometer was employed, with Ni-filtered $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation at a scanning speed of $1^\circ 28$ per minute. For IR studies (KBr) a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrometer was used, fixing the grating at 4 000, 2 000, 600 and 200 cm^{-1} . IR spectra of the separated clay fraction as such and of those heated at 110, 600 and 700° were recorded. For a rather complete mineralogical study of clay, the iron-bearing minerals present in the clay were also characterised making use of Mössbauer spectroscopy. For

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA* OF TINPAHARI BENTONITE CLAY

Constituent	<5 μm fraction	5–20 μm fraction
Loss on ignition	12.50	4.80
SiO_2	52.10	62.80
Fe_2O_3	4.70	1.85
TiO_2	0.88	0.08
MgO	2.10	1.25
K_2O	0.58	0.41
Na_2O	0.41	0.19
CaO	0.65	0.21
P_2O_5	0.14	—
Al_2O_3	25.80	28.50

* BET surface area = $158.5\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$, Cation-exchange capacity = 180 meq/100 g, for <5 μm clay fraction.

this study, the finely ground (200 mesh BSS) clay powder was sandwiched between two beryllium sheets in the sample holder mount and used as absorber for Mössbauer spectral analysis. The Mössbauer spectra were recorded, in transmission mode, at room temperature (298 K) using a constant acceleration type Mössbauer spectrometer (MBS-35) coupled with a 1024-Channel Multi Channel Analyser (MCA-38A) and data printer, the complete unit being supplied by the Electronics Corporation of India. A 100 mCi ^{57}Co γ -source (Amersham, U.K.) was matched against a natural iron foil for calibrating the equipment. All spectra were run until approximately 5×10^6 counts/channel in the baseline had been accumulated. The spectra were analysed using the isomer-shift, quadrupole splitting and hyperfine field systematics. The isomer-shift values in the present work are reported with respect to iron.

Results and Discussion

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the raw and separated fractions of the clay are essentially the

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same, evincing thereby that the grain size has no effect. It is to be mentioned here that two large peaks in the diffractograms corresponding to $2\theta=6$ and 12° at 13.9 and 7.1 Å, respectively, were observed accompanied by a relatively small peak at 3.28 Å, the latter owing to the presence of quartz. Furthermore, the intensity of this last peak was observed to be less in case of separated fractions, showing that the finer grain size fraction of the clay contains less amounts of quartz.

Ir study of the clay revealed three sharp bands at 3 620, 3 400 and 3 180 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to OH groups of different nature. Besides, additional sharp bands appearing at 1 660 and 1 400 cm^{-1} were also observed which are due to OH of H_2O bending. The ir study on clay samples heated at different temperature showed that the H_2O in the Tinpahari bentonite clay is of three types, namely, water of hydration, weakly bonded by van der Waals forces, and strongly chemically bonded. A close examination of the ir spectra (not shown) further evinces two broad bands at 1 060 and 920 cm^{-1} , the former being attributed to Si—O stretching and the latter to bending of OH linked with Al. One interesting feature of the ir spectra was that no band corresponding to the formation of OH group linked with Fe was observed.

The typical Mössbauer spectra of different fractions of Tinpahari bentonite clay is depicted in Fig. 1, and from which the Mössbauer parameters, namely, isomer-shift and quadrupole splitting values

Fig. 1. Mössbauer spectra of Tinpahari bentonite clay: (A) unseparated fraction, (B) $<5 \mu\text{m}$ fraction, and (C) $5-20 \mu\text{m}$ fraction.

have been computed. From the Mössbauer parameters of the iron containing minerals in the clay (Table 2) it is deduced that illite and chlorite are the principal iron mineral constituent in the clay.

TABLE 2—MÖSSBAUER PARAMETERS FOR TINPAHARI CLAY

Material	Isomer-shift (δ) mm s^{-1}	Quadrupole splitting (Δ) mm s^{-1}	Mineral identified
Unseparated	1.11	2.61	Illite
Tinpahari clay	1.13	2.51	Chlorite

This finding is in conformity with the observations of Weaver *et al.*⁴, who reported two Mössbauer absorption lines in montmorillonite clays due to illite and chlorite. Nevertheless, the X-ray diffraction study of the Tinpahari bentonite clay points out the presence of dioctahedral illite, chlorite and some trioctahedral vermiculite ($\text{Mg}_{2-x}\text{Fe}_x$) (Si_6Al) as the main mineral constituents. The presence of vermiculite, however, could not be conclusively ascertained from Mössbauer spectroscopy, probably because of its minute presence. As mentioned above, the X-ray diffraction patterns of the clay at room temperature and of the one heated at 200° evince rather conclusively a sharp decrease in the observed $d(001)$ value, and consequently the peak intensity at $2\theta=6^\circ$ on going from room temperature to 200° , indicating the loss of hydration of vermiculite—an observation also reported by Brown⁵. The removal of water of hydration around 120° and above as indicated in the ir spectra, also points out to the presence of vermiculite. The presence of illite is evidenced by a sharp band at 330 cm^{-1} due to SiOH bonding in the ir spectra of the raw clay, and this band vanishes completely in the spectra of the clay sample heated at 500° and above (upto 600 and 700°). This is also substantiated by the X-ray diffraction pattern of the clay heated at 600° , where the strong decrease in the peak intensity due to chlorite at $2\theta=12^\circ$ is observed. This is suggestive of the decomposition of chlorite present in the clay.

The X-ray diffraction and ir results get support from the differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the clay. The DTA curve of the clay reveals a most intense endothermic peak at 170° together with a small inflexion at 300° and another endothermic peak at 550° , besides a blunt S-shaped peak at higher temperature (around 900°). The peak at 170° is attributed to loss of pore water, and its very large intensity suggests that the clay is of highly disordered structure. The small endothermic inflexion at 300° might be due to the loss of water from close contact of the cation present in between the layers of the clay. Dehydroxylation of the clay at 550° , observed to take place in a single step, is suggestive of its behaviour as an 'abnormal montmorillonite'⁶. The low-temperature single-step dehydroxylation behaviour has been ascribed to the replacement of the Si from tetrahedral sheet by Al or of the latter by Fe or Mg⁷. The abnormality exhibited by Tinpahari clay could, thus, be attributed to the isomorphic substitution of Fe for Al in the octahedral sheet, which is evinced by

relatively high percentage of iron (Table 2) present in the clay.

From the above mineralogical studies, it is concluded that Tinpahari clay is essentially a 'mixed-layer minerals' clay, composed of dioctahedral illite, chlorite and vermiculite. In the dioctahedral illite, iron can apparently proxy for aluminium in the octahedral layer^a. One such dioctahedral illite is glauconite, with considerable replacement of Al^{III} by Fe^{III}, Fe^{II} and Mg^{II} frequently with even less than two-thirds of the possible positions filled. There is consequently a charge deficiency in the octahedral sheet as well as in the tetrahedral sheets, and the inter-layer cations (Ca²⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺) seem to balance both these charges. The clay minerals may be mixed in several ways, making them highly disordered structure (see above) and the composite clay might be regarded as gradational between illite and montmorillonite, but which is

actually composed of inter-layered mixtures of true illite, montmorillonite and other minerals^a.

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